

Cetyl pyridinium chloride catalysed reaction of acridine yellow with acidic chloramine-T

Brijesh Pare*, Manisha Ayachit and S. B. Jonnalagadda^a

Post Graduate Department of Chemistry, Madhav Science College (Vikram University),

Ujjain-456 010, Madhya Pradesh, India

E-mail : brijesh_parc@hotmail.com

^aUniversity of KwaZulu-Natal, Durban, South Africa

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Abstract : The kinetics and mechanism of the uncatalyzed and cetyl pyridinium chloride (CPC) catalyzed oxidation of acridine yellow (3,6-diamino-2,7-dimethyl acridine hydrochloride) dye by chloramine-T in acidic media has been studied spectrophotometrically. With excess concentrations of other reactants, the reaction rate follows pseudo-first order kinetics with respect to acridine yellow. The uncatalyzed reaction has fractional order dependence on chloramine-T as well as on H⁺ concentration. The catalyzed reaction follows fractional order kinetics in [CPC]. The cetyl pyridinium chloride, a cationic surfactant, catalysed the reaction even before its critical micelle concentration. This pre-micellar kinetics has been rationalized in the light of Piszkiwicz positive co-operativity model. The positive co-operativity index $n = 1.95$ has also been computed. The spectral shifts are the evidences of dye-surfactant and dye-surfactant-oxidant interactions. Variations of ionic strength has no influence on the reaction rate suggesting that neutral charged species are involved in the rate-determining step. Increase in the addition of *p*-toluenesulfonamide resulted in decrease in rate constant values. The basic stoichiometric equation is as follows : $AY^+ + ArSO_2NHCl + H_2O = P^+ + ArSO_2NH_2 + CH_3CH_2OH + CH_3CN + 2HCl$, where $P^+ = 7$ -aminoquinoline-2,3-dicarboxylic acid. On the basis of the product analysis pertinent mechanisms are proposed.

Keywords : Chloramine-T, acridine yellow, cetyl pyridinium chloride.

Introduction

Colours in the form of dyes are used by industries on a vast scale. When not consumed completely these dyes are released in the environment polluting it as well as life. Acridine class of dyes is extensively used in printing and dyeing of silk and cellulosic fibers. Acridine yellow is largely used on leather¹. Due to its stability, it has long residence time in water and is hazardous in aquatic system^{2,3}. Thus, the colour removal process and the degradation dynamics of the dye is a necessary aspect for human welfare and sustainable environment. An attempt is made to decolorize and degrade these class of dyes by using a suitable oxidation method. Therefore, oxidation of acridine yellow (AY⁺) by chloramine-T has been carried out in order to optimize the reaction conditions to develop a more efficient colour removing chemical oxidation method. Chloramine-T (*p*-Me-C₆H₄-SO₂NCINa.1.5H₂O) abbreviated, as CAT is the widely studied oxidant^{4,5}. The oxidative depletion of dye was

found to be effectively catalyzed by the cationic detergent, cetyl pyridinium chloride (CPC). Detergents have tendency to form micelles. Micelle acts as a kind of micro-reactor. The micelles may increase the reactant concentration within the hydrophilic or hydrophobic areas and cause a favorable orientation of the reactants by polarity gradients. Therefore, CPC catalyzed oxidative depletion of the AY⁺ by chloramine-T has been investigated. The addition of CPC to the dye solution brings about hyperchromic shifts. This spectral shift due to the dye surfactant interaction leads to the possibility of evolution of an analytical method for the determination of CPC surfactant that is discussed elsewhere⁶.

Experimental

The chemicals used were of AnalaR grade and the double distilled water was used throughout to prepare the solutions. An aqueous solution of chloramine-T (Merck) was prepared and standardized periodically by

the iodometric method and preserved in an amber-coloured bottle until further use. The aqueous solution of AY⁺ (Aldrich) was prepared by dissolving 0.0274 g of acridine yellow in 100 cm³ of water. Working solution was prepared by appropriate dilution of the stock solution. The stock solution of CPC (Aldrich) was prepared by dissolving 0.0358 g of CPC in 100 cm³ of water. Stock solution of H₂SO₄ was prepared by diluting the calculated volume (from density) of acid with distilled water and finally its concentration was determined by titrating it against standard NaOH solution using phenolphthalein as indicator.

Kinetic procedure :

In all experiments the pseudo-first order kinetics with respect to acridine yellow was monitored at 445 nm, using Systronics 166 UV-Vis spectrophotometer. No interference from other reagents, intermediates or product was observed at 445 nm. Beer's law was valid for the measurement under the experimental conditions considered. The total initial volume of the reaction mixture was always kept 10 ml and at 25.0 (±0.1) °C. Reagent solutions were mixed with the requisite volumes of acridine yellow, sulphuric acid, CPC and water or other reagents where necessary. Separately thermally equilibrated solution of chloramine-T was added to commence the reaction. After vigorous mixing, solution was transferred to spectrophotometer cell. In all the experiments, the reactions were followed up to two half lives.

Stoichiometry was determined using varying ratio of oxidant to acridine yellow. Solutions were thermostated at 25 °C for 48 h incubation. The absorbance at 445 nm was measured and residual CAT was determined iodometrically using standard sodium thiosulfate, potassium iodide and starch as an indicator. The mole ratio (no. of moles of oxidant consumed per mol of AY) was calculated.

The representative stoichiometry of reaction can be depicted as

where, P⁺ = 7-aminoquinoline-2,3-dicarboxylic acid.

Product analysis : The product analysis was done by mixing 1 M sulfuric acid (50 ml), AY⁺ (300 mg) and CAT (3 g). The mixture was allowed to stand for 24 h. The organic components were partitioned with diethyl ether. Using benzene-ethyl acetate mixture (8 : 2) as an eluent, preliminary studies were carried out by thin-layer chromatography. The IR spectrum of major separated sample showed absorption peak at 1388 cm⁻¹, which may be due to presence of COO⁻ stretching of carboxylic group and is further supported by the strong absorption band at 1305 cm⁻¹. Presence of carbonyl group is further substantiated by the presence of C–O stretching bands at 1159, 1097 and 1018 cm⁻¹. The absorption band at 1528 cm⁻¹ supports the N–H bending. The absorption peaks at 1599 cm⁻¹ supports the C–N stretching. Generally the O–H stretching band of the carboxylic group gets superimposed upon C–H stretching at 3261 cm⁻¹ of benzene nucleus. The strong absorption peak at 3359 cm⁻¹ indicates the presence of conjugated carboxylic acid. The band at 3448 cm⁻¹ shows NH₂ stretching. Absence of intense absorption peak between 1300–1200 cm⁻¹ indicates the absence of N–O stretching.

Therefore, oxidation at nitrogen atom and formation of N-oxide in the heterocyclic ring is unlikely. The main product was thus identified as 7-aminoquinoline-2,3-dicarboxylic acid. From this laboratory earlier also the similar products were reported in the case of oxidation of acridine orange dye with acidic chlorite⁷. Literature survey also reveals that oxidation of acridine by various oxidants such as calcium hypochlorite in the presence of cobalt, bromine and sodium methoxide, potassium permanganate and ozone yields quinoline-2,3-dicarboxylic acid as a major product⁸. Studies on the further characterization of reaction products are in progress.

Results and discussion

In a typical kinetic run, with [AY⁺] = 2.0 × 10⁻⁵ mol dm⁻³, [CAT] = 1.0 × 10⁻⁴ mol dm⁻³, [H⁺] = 1.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, a plot of log absorbance versus time is linear indicating that reaction under chosen conditions follows pseudo-first order kinetics. The mean pseudo-first order rate constant *k*_o' was found 4.63 × 10⁻⁴ s⁻¹. For the determination of dependence of oxidation reaction

on CAT, the concentration of CAT was varied over a wide range, while those of other reactants were kept constants. The Table 1 summarized the results obtained at constant ionic strength. Plot of $\log k_o'$ vs \log CAT gave a straight-line with slope 0.73 (0.99) suggesting that the reaction has fractional order dependence with respect to CAT. Double reciprocal plot of $k_o'^{-1}$ vs CAT^{-1} at constant substrate and acid concentration has been found to be complex. This kinetic evidence of complex formation between substrate and oxidant further supports the validity of the proposed mechanism. With the employed reactant concentration $[\text{AY}^+] = 2.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$, $[\text{H}^+] = 1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $[\text{CAT}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$, the initial ionic strength of reaction mixture was 0.0032. The variation of ionic strength was done from 0.0032 to 0.0212 by the addition of sodium sulphate (Table 2).

Table 1. Uncatalyzed reaction-order with respect to chloramine-T

$[\text{AY}^+] = 2.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{H}^+] = 1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$

[CAT] ($10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$)	k_o' (10^{-4} s^{-1}) ^a
1.0	4.63
2.0	6.83
3.0	9.12
4.0	11.37
5.0	13.65
6.0	15.83
7.0	18.07
8.0	20.31
9.0	22.55

^aMean of duplicate experiments.

Reaction was studied at different concentrations of CPC while keeping the other factors constant. On addition of surfactant solution the reaction rate increases sharply. The results are summarized in Table 3. Here, CPC catalyzes the reaction even in the pre-micellar region (0.5×10^{-4} to $3.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$). The reported CMC of CPC is $9.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$ at 25 °C. The role of surfactant catalysis has been rationalized in the light of various models such as Piskiewicz model, Hill model and Menger model. Addition of CPC to the solution of acridine yellow does not produce turbidity and a clear solution was obtained. The spectral studies revealed a

bathochromic shift from 445 to 450 nm in the presence of CPC. This provides an evidence for the interaction of CPC with the acridine yellow. Since the dye molecule and surfactant both are cationic in nature, thus obviously the cause of interaction is hydrophobic that overweighs the electronic repulsion. This interaction results in penetration of dye molecules in to the micelles. This interactive localization of the reacting species in the relatively small volume of the pseudo-micellar phase compared to the bulk solution leads to a large increase in the effective concentration and the observed rate increases accordingly. Reports are available for pre-micellar catalysis^{9,10} suggesting that substrate promotes micellization of cationic surfactants and small aggregates of the detergent exist below the CMC and they catalyze the reaction. The catalysis by CPC has therefore been treated by a scheme proposed by Piskiewicz¹¹. This scheme includes the decomposition of substrate micelle complex in to the free components; resulting in an equation of the following form :

$$\log (k_{\text{obs}} - k_o') / (k_m - k_{\text{obs}}) = n \log [D] - \log k_D$$

From the above equation the plot of $\log (k_{\text{obs}} - k_o') / (k_m - k_{\text{obs}})$ vs $\log [D]$ is linear with a slope $n = 1.95$ called the index of co-operativity.

Table 2. Effect of addition of *p*-toluenesulfonamide and variation of ionic strength

$[\text{AY}^+] = 2.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{H}^+] = 1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$,

$[\text{CAT}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$

Ionic strength (mol dm^{-3})	k_o' (10^{-3} s^{-1}) ^a	[PTS] × 10^{-3}	k_o' (10^{-3} s^{-1}) ^a
0.0032	4.63	1.0	5.40
0.0062	4.90	2.0	5.03
0.0092	4.75	3.0	3.95
0.0122	4.70	4.0	3.15
0.0152	4.95	5.0	2.45
0.0182	4.75	6.0	2.22

^aMean of duplicate experiments.

The effect of PTS, one of the end product in chloramine-T oxidations on the rate of oxidation was studied by taking various concentrations of PTS keeping the concentrations of other reactant constant at constant temperature. Oxidation rate is decreased with the increase in the concentration of PTS. The decrease in reaction rate supports our consideration

that HOCl is main oxidizing species in accordance with the following equilibrium¹².

Table 3. CPC-catalyzed reaction

[AY⁺] = 2.0 × 10⁻⁵ mol dm⁻³, [H⁺] = 1.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³,

[CAT] = 1.0 × 10⁻⁴ mol dm⁻³

[CPC] (10 ⁻⁴ mol dm ⁻³)	k _o ' (10 ⁻³ s ⁻¹) ^a
0	4.63
0.5	6.50
0.7	7.67
0.9	8.83
1.0	9.83
3.0	15.56
5.0	14.85
7.0	11.56

^aMean of duplicate runs.

Rate law :

Bathochromic shift in presence of the oxidant is the spectroscopic evidence of interaction between the dye molecule and CPC. The rate equation for the uncatalyzed reaction between AY⁺ and CAT can be represented as follows :

$$r = -d[\text{AY}^+]/dt = k_o [\text{AY}^+] [\text{CAT}]^{2/3} \quad (1)$$

when [CAT] is excess, the above equation reduces to

$$r = k_o' [\text{AY}^+] \quad (2)$$

where the pseudo-first order rate constant for uncatalyzed reaction is k_o' = k_o [CAT]^{2/3}.

In the presence of the CPC, the oxidation reaction proceeds through both uncatalyzed and catalyzed pathways. Therefore, the following equation represents the rate of depletion of AY⁺ in the presence of catalyst under excess [CAT] and acid concentrations :

$$-d[\text{AY}^+]/dt = (k_o' + k_c' [\text{CPC}]) [\text{AY}^+] \quad (3)$$

$$= k_o'' [\text{AY}^+] \quad (4)$$

where k_c' = k_c [CAT]^{2/3} and k_o'' = {k_o' + k_c' [CPC]}

If eq. (4) holds, a plot of the observed pseudo-first order rate constant in the presence of catalyst, k_o'' vs [CPC] should give a straight line with intercept equal to k_o'. The intercept value 4.67 × 10⁻⁴ s⁻¹ is in close agreement with rate constant value 4.63 × 10⁻⁴ s⁻¹.

Mechanism :

Chloramine-T behaves as a strong electrolyte and in acidic media it furnishes various oxidising species.

(N-Chloro toluene-p-sulfonamide)

Scheme 1

Scheme 2

(Dichloramine-T)

(Hypochlorous acid)

(Protonated species)

In our experimental studies the rate of reaction is retarded by addition of PTS, which suggests that the eq. (9) must be preceded by rate determining step. The neutral salt effect supports the participation of neutral molecule in rate determining step. HOCl may be considered as the main oxidizing species for the reaction, which proceeds slowly in sulfuric acid. The linear double reciprocal plot with intercept on Y-axis of k^{-1} vs CAT^{-1} suggests the formation of a complex between substrate and oxidant⁶. On this basis the mechanism has been envisaged (Scheme 1).

Surfactant catalyzed mechanism :

Addition of aqueous solution of CPC to the solution of acridine yellow shows hyperchromic shift. The cause of interaction is electrostatic interaction that overweighs the electronic repulsion. This interactive localization of the reacting species in the relatively small volume of the micelles compared to the bulk solution leads to a large increase in the effective concentration

and as a result the observed rate (in terms of moles per unit time per litre of the entire solution). In the present case as described earlier in the Piszkiwicz model, Menger and Portney's model we have seen that there is a substrate promoted micellization and a pseudo phase has also come into exist. We propose the following reaction mechanism (Scheme 2) in the presence of CPC.

The chemistry of remaining reaction scheme is same as for the uncatalyzed reaction. The Scheme 2 is proposed for catalysis by CPC. As per the reaction mechanism proposed by Bruice *et al.*¹³, assumption begins with the interaction of substrate AY^+ and a number of D molecules aggregate to form catalytic micelles.

Bathochromic shift is the spectroscopic evidence of association of the dye with the detergent. The chemistry of remaining reaction scheme is same as for the uncatalyzed reaction.

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